

A conjecture about twin primes

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1 Introduction

In this very short article, I will present a conjecture about twin primes, which inevitably recalls the conjecture on prime numbers, exposed in one of my previous articles.

2 The conjecture

Conjecture. There are infinite formulas of the form

$$f(n) = n^2 - n + p,$$

with n , which is a positive natural number less than p , which is a prime number, that generate at least one different pair of twin primes.